

Artificial intelligence applications in agriculture: a systematic review of literature

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming agriculture by offering innovative solutions to persistent challenges. This systematic literature review explores the most studied AI applications in agriculture, emphasizing crop management, agronomic decision-making, early detection of diseases and pests, and climate change adaptation. Using the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) methodology, 700 publications were retrieved from databases such as Scopus, ScienceDirect, and IEEE Xplore, with 104 relevant articles selected after applying strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. The findings underscore the importance of machine learning and image processing in tailoring agronomic practices to specific plot conditions and microclimates. These tools enable early identification and control of plant diseases and pests, reducing crop losses and dependence on chemicals. Nonetheless, challenges remain, particularly regarding accessibility for smallholder farmers, high implementation costs, and limited data infrastructure. While AI offers significant potential to enhance agricultural productivity, sustainability, and resilience, addressing these limitations is crucial. A balanced, inclusive approach is essential to ensure AI's benefits are widely distributed and contribute to long-term food security and environmental sustainability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture has evolved through technological advances, new farming practices, and tools to improve food production and resource management [1]–[3]. It began as subsistence agriculture [4], where communities relied on hunting, gathering, and early domestication of plants and animals [5]. The development of farming techniques and primitive tools boosted food production and storage, enabling permanent settlements and the rise of early agricultural civilizations [6], [7]. This process led to today's precision agriculture era [8].

The agricultural revolution around 10,000 B.C. marked a pivotal shift with the introduction of advanced cultivation and domestication techniques, such as crop rotation and selective breeding [9], [10], significantly boosting food production and enabling population growth. Over the centuries, agricultural innovation persisted [11], with milestones like crop rotation in the middle ages and the 18th-century revolution marked by technologies such as iron plowing [12], [13] and sowing selected seeds [14]. In the 20th century, the green revolution introduced high-yielding crop varieties and widespread use of fertilizers and pesticides [13], which greatly increased production but also raised concerns about environmental impact and

sustainability [13]–[16]. Looking ahead, agriculture must address rising demands. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) projects the global population will exceed 9 billion by 2050, requiring a 60–70% increase in agricultural output [17]. In this context, innovation becomes critical. According to the World Bank, agricultural innovation and technology are essential for poverty reduction in developing regions [18], where nearly 80% of the extreme poor live in rural areas and rely on agriculture for their livelihoods. Therefore, sustainable technological advances in agriculture are not only vital for food security but also for socioeconomic development and environmental preservation. Today, we are in the midst of a transition towards precision agriculture and the application of information and communication technologies (ICT) in farm management [19], [20]. Technologies like sensors, drones, geographic information systems (GIS), and data analysis optimize resources and efficiency [21], [22]. Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are increasingly applied in decision making [23] and in the early detection of diseases and pests [24], [25].

The use of AI in agriculture has grown significantly in recent years [26], [27], transforming crop management, decision-making, and production challenges. The integration of information technology, data analytics, and machine learning has enabled diverse AI applications [28]–[30] aimed at improving efficiency, productivity, and sustainability [31]. These applications include early detection of crop diseases [32], [33] monitoring of climatic conditions, and optimization of irrigation and fertilizer use [34]. AI also supports automation through robots and drones [35]–[37] and enhances decision-making with real-time data analysis [38].

This systematic review analyzes the most researched AI applications in agriculture, focusing on efficiency, decision making, sustainability, production quality, and ethical-economic challenges. It also explores how AI is transforming modern agricultural practices. The article is structured in five sections: i) introduction presents AI's transformative role, ii) methodology explains the selection of 104 studies using preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA), iii) results highlight applications such as irrigation and pest detection, iv) discussion examines benefits and implementation barriers, and v) conclusion underscores the need for equitable, sustainable AI adoption in the agricultural sector.

2. METHODOLOGY

This paper follows a structured approach to collect and analyze information. First, the PRISMA methodology was applied [39] to identify the most relevant articles. Second, bibliometric analysis was used [40] to detect common terms influencing the study of AI-based digital applications in agriculture. Lastly, key statistical factors and methods were reviewed in relation to bibliometric findings. According to PRISMA, the systematic review is structured into: i) type of study, ii) research questions, iii) search strategy, and iv) inclusion and exclusion criteria.

2.1. Type of study

A systematic review of the literature was used to prepare this article [41]. This process allows for the collection of relevant evidence on a given topic that. In addition to meeting the established eligibility criteria, provides answers to the research questions posed [42].

2.2. Research questions

Five questions were developed to cover the objectives and to identify relevant characteristics to answer the following research questions:

RQ1. What are the most researched AI applications in the agricultural sector based on published studies?

RQ2. What is the role of AI in the early detection and control of plant diseases and crop pests?

RQ3. How has AI influenced the customization of agricultural practices and adaptation to different climatic and soil conditions?

RQ4. How has AI influenced agricultural decision making, such as crop management, irrigation scheduling and fertilizer application?

2.3. Search strategy

This systematic review employed various strategies, terms, and resources to identify relevant studies on AI applications in agriculture [43]. Table 1 presents the search equations and terms used. In order to answer the research questions posed, articles were collected from the main databases such as: Scopus, IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, IOPscience, EBSCOhost, Taylor & Francis. A total of 700 articles were collected, using inclusion and exclusion criteria, which allowed the identification of 104 relevant articles, as shown in Figure 1.

Table 1. Search equations

Database	Equations
Scopus	"artificial intelligence" AND "AI" AND "agriculture" AND "cultivation"; "artificial intelligence" AND "AI" AND "agriculture"
ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore, IOPscience	"artificial intelligence" AND ("smart farming" OR "intelligent agriculture" OR "intelligent farming")
EBSCOhost, Taylor & Francis	("artificial intelligence" OR "AI") AND ("smart farming" OR "intelligent agriculture" OR "intelligent farming")

Figure 1. Selection methodology diagram

2.4. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

For the systematic review study, the following inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied, as shown in Table 2. These were established to ensure that the selected studies were relevant and up to date. Their application helped maintain the quality and consistency of the review.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion	Exclusion
Studies investigating the most researched applications of AI in agriculture.	Studies that focus solely on the description of AI technologies without analyzing their application in agriculture.
Studies published in the last 8 years to ensure that the information is up to date.	Studies that focus only on the description of AI technologies without analyzing their application in agriculture.
Studies in languages relevant to your research.	Studies that do not provide sufficient detailed information on their methods and results.
Studies addressing different areas of AI application in agriculture, such as crop management, disease detection, and resource optimization	Duplicate studies found in multiple databases.

3. RESULTS

We analyzed 700 articles found in the database related to the research topic, of which 7 duplicate articles were rejected or did not contribute to the same research topic. After reviewing the articles, 693 articles were selected, 589 articles were excluded according to the exclusion criteria and did not contribute to answer the research question. We obtained 104 articles for systematic review as shown in Figure 2.

Bibliographic analysis allows the extraction of documents by identifying co-occurring words to detect patterns related to authors' work [40]. Bibliometrics measures scientific activity publications, citations, and collaborations and helps identify trends in a research field [44]. VOSviewer [45] is a tool used to analyze and visualize co-authorship, citation, and keyword networks [46] enabling graphical representations of scientific relationships. Based on this, visualization maps were generated as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 4 presents a word cloud generated from the analysis of the articles systematized in this review, offering a perspective on the most frequent themes and concepts in the field of study. Among the most prominent words are "agriculture," "machine learning," "deep learning," and "prediction". Figure 5 shows a tree map from a bibliometric analysis illustrating the most recurrent keywords in AI and agriculture research. The most frequent terms are "artificial intelligence" (8%), "deep learning" (5%), and both "agriculture" and "machine learning" (4% each). This visualization highlights the predominant themes and reflects current research focus areas in the application of AI to agriculture.

Figure 5. Tree map

Figure 6 presents the classification of the 104 articles analyzed, categorized according to the continent and the database in which they were published. The graph reveals that the largest amount of research on the application of AI in agriculture comes from the Asian continent. In addition, it is observed that these investigations are mainly concentrated in the Scopus database. The Figure 7 illustrates the number of articles published per year, broken down according to the source database: Scopus, IEEE Xplore, EBSCOhost, IOPscience, and ScienceDirect. In particular, it is noted that, in the year 2022, ScienceDirect registered a significantly high number of articles in relation to the search criteria used.

Figure 6. Articles by database and continent

Figure 7. Articles by year and database

4. DISCUSSION

In this systematic review of the scientific literature, we analyze the most researched AI applications in agriculture, identify the most used models and algorithms, as well as their influence in different fields of agriculture, in order to answer the proposed questions.

4.1. Answer to research questions

4.1.1. RQ1: what are the most researched AI applications in the agricultural sector based on published studies?

Figure 8 shows the articles related to this topic, highlighting the most researched AI applications: "Disease and pest detection" with 32 articles, "Irrigation optimization" with 19 articles, and "Crop selection and breeding" with 17 articles. These areas represent the main focus of AI research in agriculture. They reflect the growing interest in improving crop health, resource management and genetic advances through AI technologies.

Figure 8. Articles by AI applications

From Table 3 it can be seen that AI-based applications are transforming various aspects of agriculture, from the detection of plant health problems, with the use of machine learning algorithms to identify and predict plant diseases and pests. These applications enable a faster and more accurate response to production optimization and resource management. AI applications are becoming more intelligent over time, thanks to machine learning, which allows them to further improve production operations.

Table 3. AI Applications used in the agricultural sector

Application of AI in agriculture	Description	Articles
Disease and pest detection	Use of machine learning algorithms to identify and predict plant diseases and pests, enabling a faster and more accurate response	[47]–[78]
Irrigation optimization	Use of sensors and algorithms to determine the optimal timing and amount of irrigation, based on real-time data of soil and weather conditions	[79]–[97]
Fertilization management	AI application to recommend the amount and type of fertilizers to be used, considering soil composition and specific crop needs	[98]–[105]
Crop classification and harvesting	Implementation of computer vision algorithms for sorting and selecting ripe crops for harvesting, reducing waste and optimizing yields	[106]–[117]
Climate forecasting and management	Use of historical and real-time climate data together with AI models to predict weather patterns, enabling informed decision making in agricultural management.	[118]–[123]
Control of agricultural robots and drones	AI used to guide and control robots and drones in agricultural tasks such as planting, crop monitoring, and pesticide application	[124]–[132]
Crop selection and breeding	Application of machine learning techniques to analyze genetic and phenotypic data and predict desirable crop traits, accelerating the breeding process.	[133]–[149]

Figure 9 shows studies that apply the above techniques and algorithms in specific agricultural contexts. These examples illustrate how different AI approaches have been used to address various challenges in agriculture. Table 4 groups the main applications of AI in agriculture according to the AI technique used as applied to agriculture. This table provides key examples of how different AI techniques and algorithms have been applied in agriculture. Among the techniques can be identified: supervised machine

learning, deep learning, sensor networks, machine learning, fuzzy logic, unsupervised machine learning, and artificial neural networks.

Figure 9. Applications by AI model and technique

Table 4. AI applications used in the agricultural sector

Application of AI in agriculture	AI technique	Articles
Disease and pest detection	Supervised machine learning	[49], [51], [53], [54], [56]–[59], [70]–[72], [74]–[76]
	Deep learning	[47], [52], [55], [60]–[69], [77]
	Sensor networks	[73], [78]
	Fuzzy logic	[48]
Irrigation optimization	Supervised machine learning	[85], [88], [91], [93], [94]
	Sensor networks	[84], [89], [92], [97]
	Deep learning	[79], [80], [82]
	Fuzzy logic	[83], [86], [87]
	Machine learning	[81]
	Artificial neural networks	[90]
	Supervised machine learning	[134], [136], [137], [139]–[141], [143], [144], [148]
Crop selection and breeding	Machine learning	[133], [135], [147]
	Deep learning	[142], [146]
	Unsupervised machine learning	[145]
	Fuzzy logic	[138]
	Supervised machine learning	[107], [110], [111], [115], [116]
Crop classification and harvesting	Deep learning	[108], [109], [112]
	Machine learning	[106], [113], [114]
	Unsupervised machine learning	[117]
	Sensor networks	[124], [125], [127], [128]
	Unsupervised machine learning	[130], [131]
Control of agricultural robots and drones	Supervised machine learning	[126], [129]
	Deep learning	[132]
	Supervised machine learning	[99], [102], [105]
	Sensor networks	[103], [104]
Fertilization management	Machine learning	[100], [101]
	Deep learning	[98]
	Supervised machine learning	[118]
	Artificial neural networks	[121]
	Unsupervised machine learning	[120]
Climate forecasting and management	Fuzzy logic	[123]
	Sensor networks	[119]

Figure 10 analyzes the types of AI techniques used in agriculture. "Supervised machine learning" leads with 39 articles, enabling plant disease detection, crop classification, and weed identification through image analysis [150]. "Deep learning" follows with 24 articles, using recurrent neural networks (RNN) and generative adversarial networks (GAN) to forecast crop yields from climatic data and generate synthetic images for training disease detection models. Table 5 and Figure 11 show the models or algorithms used in AI applications in the agricultural sector. Among the most prominent are: convolutional neural networks (CNN), support vector machines (SVM), linear regression (LR), and random forest (RF).

Figure 10. Articles on AI techniques and their application in agriculture

Table 5. AI model algorithm used in the agricultural sector

Model-algorithm	Application of AI in agriculture	Articles
CNN	Disease and pest detection	[47], [49], [54], [55], [59]–[64], [66], [67], [69], [71], [77]
	Crop classification and harvesting	[108]–[112], [116]
	Crop selection and breeding	[133], [140], [143]
	Fertilization management	[99], [102]
	Control of agricultural robots and drones	[129]
SVM	Crop selection and breeding	[146], [148]
	Irrigation optimization	[85], [94]
	Disease and pest detection	[58]
LR	Crop classification and harvesting	[113]
	Disease and pest detection	[75]
	Fertilization management	[100]
	Irrigation optimization	[88]
RF	Crop selection and breeding	[147]
	Crop selection and breeding	[136], [141]
	Climatology forecasting and management	[118]
	Irrigation optimization	[91]

Figure 11. Articles by application and AI algorithm

4.1.2. RQ2. What is the role of AI in the early detection and control of plant diseases and crop pests?

Figure 12 shows the articles analyzed for the role of AI in the early detection and control of plant and crop diseases. Such studies that apply AI in the early detection and control of plant diseases and crop pests. These examples illustrate how AI has revolutionized the ability of farmers to identify and manage plant health problems more efficiently.

Figure 12. Articles by relevance in the detection of diseases and pests

Table 6 analyzes the most researched AI applications for detecting and controlling diseases and pests in agriculture. For early detection, image analysis of leaves and crops helps identify disease patterns, while sensors monitor environmental changes indicating plant health issues. For control, AI enables precise treatment application, predictive models to forecast outbreaks, sensor-based alerts, and algorithms to anticipate disease and pest spread and implement preventive actions.

Table 6. Articles analyzed according to AI applications in the detection and control of diseases and pests

Role of AI in detection and control	AI applications	Articles
Control of diseases and pests	IoT and sensors	[50], [78]
	Predictive models	[68], [112]
Early detection of diseases and pests	Image analysis (classification or segmentation)	[47]–[49], [51], [53]–[63], [65]–[67], [69], [70], [72], [77]
	IoT and sensors	[73], [74]

4.1.3. RQ3. How has AI influenced the customization of farming practices and adaptation to different climatic and soil conditions?

AI offers great opportunities to improve farming practices, the present graph of Figure 13 shows studies that apply AI in customizing farming practices and adapting to changing conditions. These studies illustrate how AI has enabled farmers to adapt their strategies to specific environments and circumstances to optimize production and sustainability. Table 7 groups how AI has influenced the customization of agricultural practices and adaptation to different climatic and soil conditions.

Figure 13. Articles on the influence of AI on the customization of agricultural practices and adaptation to climatic conditions

Table 7. Articles by influence on the customization of agricultural practices and adaptation to different climatic and soil conditions

AI influence category	AI applications	Articles
Adaptation to changing conditions	Climate and pest forecasting	[47]–[52], [54]–[60], [62]–[65], [67]–[70], [72], [74], [75], [77], [78], [111]
	Climate change	[121]
	Soil variability	[81], [84], [94], [98], [118]–[120]
Customization of agricultural practices	Management recommendations	[61], [82], [83], [85], [88], [99], [100], [101], [104], [107], [110], [113], [116], [117], [122], [125], [127], [130], [133], [135]–[137], [139], [141], [146], [148], [151]
	Planting and harvest planning	[53], [79], [87], [89]–[91], [93], [96], [97], [114], [132], [138]
	Precision agricultura	[66], [73], [80], [86], [92], [95], [102], [103], [106], [108], [109], [112], [115], [124], [126], [128], [129], [131], [134], [140], [142], [147], [149]

4.1.4. RQ4. How has AI influenced agricultural decision making, such as crop management, irrigation scheduling and fertilizer application?

Figure 14 shows studies that address AI applications in crop management, irrigation scheduling and fertilizer application. These articles illustrate how AI has influenced agricultural decision making to improve efficiency and sustainability. Table 8 summarizes AI's impact on agricultural decision-making, especially in crop management. It highlights yield prediction using climate and soil data with machine learning, irrigation optimization through sensor analysis, and real-time fertilizer adjustments based on soil nutrients. AI also recommends fertilizer types and amounts by analyzing soil and crop characteristics, enhancing precision and efficiency in managing essential aspects of crop production.

Figure 14. Articles on the influence of AI in agricultural decision making

Table 8. Articles grouped by the influence of artificial AI in agricultural decision making

Decision-making category	AI applications	Articles
Crop management	Crop recommendation	[88], [108]–[110], [114], [116], [119], [131], [133], [139]–[142], [147]–[149]
	Crop yield prediction	[94], [95], [106], [113], [115], [117], [134]–[136], [138], [146]
	Pest and disease management	[47]–[51], [53]–[70], [72]–[75], [77], [78], [111], [112]
Fertilizer application	Fertilization monitoring	[98]
	Fertilizer recommendation	[99]–[104]
Irrigation scheduling	Forecast-based irrigation	[80], [121], [122], [130]
	Irrigation optimization	[79], [81]–[87], [89], [90], [92], [97], [107], [118], [120], [127], [128], [132], [137], [151]

4.2. Challenges and limitation

Although AI offers significant benefits in agriculture, its implementation faces challenges, especially in developing regions. The effectiveness of AI models can be limited by variable field conditions and poor technological infrastructure, including lack of internet access and specialized equipment [152], [153]. In addition, reliance on large data volumes is problematic where infrastructure cannot support efficient data management. High implementation costs also limit access for smallholder farmers, increasing inequality. The lack of training in AI tools further hinders adoption, highlighting the need for education and support programs. Cultural resistance and preference for traditional methods are additional barriers. Addressing these issues is essential to ensure AI becomes a practical and inclusive tool. Current research must focus on adapting AI solutions to local conditions, as many are designed for broad markets and may not suit specific microclimates or soils. Further studies on AI’s potential to support long-term agricultural sustainability particularly in biodiversity and soil health are also critical. Moreover, AI can assist in climate change adaptation, especially in vulnerable regions [154]. These research areas are key to maximizing AI’s positive impact and advancing global agricultural sustainability.

4.3. Future directions

Future directions in AI for agriculture should prioritize accessibility and adaptability across diverse environments. Research must focus on models that function with limited data and in challenging conditions, ensuring ease of use for smallholder farmers. Integrating AI with traditional farming practices can support adoption while respecting local customs. Additionally, further study is needed on AI’s role in long-term sustainability and the inclusion of small-scale producers-areas still underexplored. Advancing these lines of inquiry will help maximize AI’s potential, ensuring equitable, effective, and sustainable benefits for all agricultural communities.

5. CONCLUSION

The systematic literature review on AI applications in agriculture highlights how these technologies are transforming the industry. AI has improved efficiency, sustainability, and productivity in key areas such as crop improvement, irrigation, and pest and disease detection. It has revolutionized decision-making by enabling the customization of agricultural practices based on soil, climate, and crop conditions, resulting in better resource use and reduced phytosanitary risks. Significant impacts are evident in crop management, especially in pest and disease control and crop recommendation using historical and soil data. AI also enables early detection and control of diseases and pests through image analysis, IoT, and sensors, allowing for quick and accurate responses. Moreover, AI supports climate change adaptation by analyzing climatic data and predictive models, helping farmers minimize negative effects. However, challenges remain regarding ethical, economic, and privacy concerns, which must be addressed to ensure equitable access and responsible use. In summary, the systematic review underscores that AI has triggered a profound change in the way food production is grown and managed. The opportunities for improving efficiency, sustainability and resilience in agriculture are abundant and continue to evolve as AI advances and becomes even more integrated into the agricultural industry.

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C : **C**onceptualization

M : **M**ethodology

So : **S**oftware

Va : **V**alidation

Fo : **F**ormal analysis

I : **I**nvestigation

R : **R**esources

D : **D**ata Curation

O : Writing - **O**riginal Draft

E : Writing - Review & **E**ditng

Vi : **V**isualization

Su : **S**upervision

P : **P**roject administration

Fu : **F**unding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

Not applicable.

DATA AVAILABILITY

This study is a systematic review of literature. All data analyzed during this study are derived from previously published sources, which are cited in the manuscript. No new data were generated or collected by the authors for this review.

REFERENCES

- [1] G. Kuehne *et al.*, "Predicting farmer uptake of new agricultural practices: a tool for research, extension and policy," *Agricultural Systems*, vol. 156, pp. 115–125, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.agsy.2017.06.007.
- [2] K. Takahashi, R. Muraoka, and K. Otsuka, "Technology adoption, impact, and extension in developing countries' agriculture: a review of the recent literature," *Agricultural Economics*, vol. 51, no. 1, pp. 31–45, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1111/agec.12539.
- [3] G. N. Curry *et al.*, "Disruptive innovation in agriculture: socio-cultural factors in technology adoption in the developing world," *Journal of Rural Studies*, vol. 88, pp. 422–431, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.07.022.
- [4] P. Thibodeau, "Greek and roman agriculture," in *A Companion to Science, Technology, and Medicine in Ancient Greece and Rome*, Wiley, 2016, pp. 517–532, doi: 10.1002/9781118373057.ch32.
- [5] J. Diamond, "Evolution, consequences and future of plant and animal domestication," *Nature*, vol. 418, no. 6898, pp. 700–707, Aug. 2002, doi: 10.1038/nature01019.
- [6] A. N. Angelakis *et al.*, "Irrigation of world agricultural lands: evolution through the millennia," *Water*, vol. 12, no. 5, May 2020, doi: 10.3390/w12051285.
- [7] M. Valipour *et al.*, "The evolution of agricultural drainage from the earliest times to the present," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3390/su12010416.
- [8] C.-L. Lee, R. Strong, and K. E. Dooley, "Analyzing precision agriculture adoption across the globe: a systematic review of scholarship from 1999–2020," *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 18, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.3390/su131810295.
- [9] R. J. Cook, "Toward cropping systems that enhance productivity and sustainability," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 103, no. 49, pp. 18389–18394, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1073/pnas.0605946103.
- [10] J. Weiner, "Applying plant ecological knowledge to increase agricultural sustainability," *Journal of Ecology*, vol. 105, no. 4, pp. 865–870, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1111/1365-2745.12792.
- [11] L. Ponisio and P. Ehrlich, "Diversification, yield and a new agricultural revolution: problems and prospects," *Sustainability*, vol. 8, no. 11, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.3390/su8111118.
- [12] H. Zhao, Y. Huang, Z. Liu, W. Liu, and Z. Zheng, "Applications of discrete element method in the research of agricultural machinery: a review," *Agriculture*, vol. 11, no. 5, May 2021, doi: 10.3390/agriculture11050425.
- [13] P. L. Pingali, "Green revolution: impacts, limits, and the path ahead," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 109, no. 31, pp. 12302–12308, Jul. 2012, doi: 10.1073/pnas.0912953109.
- [14] R. E. Evenson and D. Gollin, "Assessing the impact of the green revolution, 1960 to 2000," *Science*, vol. 300, no. 5620, pp. 758–762, May 2003, doi: 10.1126/science.1078710.
- [15] J. M. Jez, S. G. Lee, and A. M. Sherp, "The next green movement: plant biology for the environment and sustainability," *Science*, vol. 353, no. 6305, pp. 1241–1244, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1126/science.aag1698.
- [16] D. T. Armanda, J. B. Guinée, and A. Tukker, "The second green revolution: innovative urban agriculture's contribution to food security and sustainability—a review," *Global Food Security*, vol. 22, pp. 13–24, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.gfs.2019.08.002.
- [17] FAO, "World agriculture in the perspective of the year 2050 (in Spanish: *La agricultura mundial en la perspectiva del año 2050*)," *Food and Agriculture Organization*, pp. 1–4, 2009.
- [18] Banco Mundial, "Agricultural innovation and technology are the key to reducing poverty in developing countries (in Spanish: *La innovación agrícola y la tecnología son la clave para reducir la pobreza en los países en desarrollo*)," *Grupo Banco Mundial*, 2019. Accessed: Aug. 15, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bancomundial.org/es/news/press-release/2019/09/16/agricultural-innovation-technology-hold-key-to-poverty-reduction-in-developing-countries-says-world-bank-report>
- [19] K. Toriyama, "Development of precision agriculture and ICT application thereof to manage spatial variability of crop growth," *Soil Science and Plant Nutrition*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 811–819, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1080/00380768.2020.1791675.
- [20] W. Liu, X.-F. Shao, C.-H. Wu, and P. Qiao, "A systematic literature review on applications of information and communication technologies and blockchain technologies for precision agriculture development," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 298, May 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126763.
- [21] H. S. Abdullahi, F. Mahieddine, and R. E. Sheriff, "Technology impact on agricultural productivity: a review of precision agriculture using unmanned aerial vehicles," in *International conference on wireless and satellite systems*, 2015, pp. 388–400, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-25479-1_29.
- [22] H. Jawad, R. Nordin, S. Gharghan, A. Jawad, and M. Ismail, "Energy-efficient wireless sensor networks for precision agriculture: a review," *Sensors*, vol. 17, no. 8, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.3390/s17081781.
- [23] J. Lindblom, C. Lundström, M. Ljung, and A. Jonsson, "Promoting sustainable intensification in precision agriculture: review of decision support systems development and strategies," *Precision Agriculture*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 309–331, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1007/s11119-016-9491-4.
- [24] S. Coulibaly, B. Kamsu-Foguem, D. Kamissoko, and D. Traore, "Deep learning for precision agriculture: a bibliometric analysis," *Intelligent Systems with Applications*, vol. 16, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.iswa.2022.200102.
- [25] T. Saranya, C. Deisy, S. Sridevi, and K. S. M. Anbananthen, "A comparative study of deep learning and internet of things for precision agriculture," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 122, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2023.106034.

- [26] R. Sharma, "Artificial intelligence in agriculture: a review," in *2021 5th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS)*, May 2021, pp. 937–942, doi: 10.1109/ICICCS51141.2021.9432187.
- [27] V. Sachithra and L. D. C. S. Subhashini, "How artificial intelligence uses to achieve the agriculture sustainability: systematic review," *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, vol. 8, pp. 46–59, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.aiaa.2023.04.002.
- [28] A. Chlingaryan, S. Sukkarieh, and B. Whelan, "Machine learning approaches for crop yield prediction and nitrogen status estimation in precision agriculture: a review," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 151, pp. 61–69, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2018.05.012.
- [29] K. Liakos, P. Busato, D. Moshou, S. Pearson, and D. Bochtis, "Machine learning in agriculture: a review," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 8, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.3390/s18082674.
- [30] L. Benos, A. C. Tagarakis, G. Dolias, R. Berruto, D. Kateris, and D. Bochtis, "Machine learning in agriculture: a comprehensive updated review," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 11, May 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21113758.
- [31] R. Sharma, S. S. Kamble, A. Gunasekaran, V. Kumar, and A. Kumar, "A systematic literature review on machine learning applications for sustainable agriculture supply chain performance," *Computers & Operations Research*, vol. 119, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.cor.2020.104926.
- [32] A. Kamilaris and F. X. Prenafeta-Boldú, "Deep learning in agriculture: a survey," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 147, pp. 70–90, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2018.02.016.
- [33] S. P. Mohanty, D. P. Hughes, and M. Salathé, "Using deep learning for image-based plant disease detection," *Frontiers in Plant Science*, vol. 7, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.3389/fpls.2016.01419.
- [34] E. Bwambale, F. K. Abagale, and G. K. Anonu, "Smart irrigation monitoring and control strategies for improving water use efficiency in precision agriculture: a review," *Agricultural Water Management*, vol. 260, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.agwat.2021.107324.
- [35] K. Jha, A. Doshi, P. Patel, and M. Shah, "A comprehensive review on automation in agriculture using artificial intelligence," *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, vol. 2, pp. 1–12, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.aiaa.2019.05.004.
- [36] T. Talaviya, D. Shah, N. Patel, H. Yagnik, and M. Shah, "Implementation of artificial intelligence in agriculture for optimisation of irrigation and application of pesticides and herbicides," *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, vol. 4, pp. 58–73, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.aiaa.2020.04.002.
- [37] A. Subeesh and C. R. Mehta, "Automation and digitization of agriculture using artificial intelligence and internet of things," *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, vol. 5, pp. 278–291, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.aiaa.2021.11.004.
- [38] B. D. Thakare and D. V. Rojatar, "A Review on smart agriculture using IoT," in *2021 6th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICES)*, Coimbatre, India, Jul. 2021, pp. 500–502, doi: 10.1109/ICES51350.2021.9489109.
- [39] M. J. Page *et al.*, "The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews," *BMJ*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.
- [40] N. Donthu, S. Kumar, D. Mukherjee, N. Pandey, and W. M. Lim, "How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: an overview and guidelines," *Journal of Business Research*, vol. 133, pp. 285–296, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070.
- [41] C. Wohlin, P. Runeson, M. Höst, M. C. Ohlsson, B. Regnell, and A. Wesslén, "Systematic literature reviews," in *Experimentation in Software Engineering*, Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2012, pp. 45–54, doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-29044-2_4.
- [42] E. T. Rother, "Systematic review X narrative review, (in Portuguese: *Revisão sistemática X revisão narrativa*)," *Acta Paulista de Enfermagem*, vol. 20, no. 2, Jun. 2007, doi: 10.1590/S0103-21002007000200001.
- [43] G. Meza-Salcedo, G. A. Rubio-Rodríguez, L. X. Mesa, and A. Blandón, "Formative and pedagogical nature of the literature review in research (in Spanish: *Carácter formativo y pedagógico de la revisión de literatura en la investigación*)," *Información Tecnológica*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 153–162, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.4067/S0718-07642020000500153.
- [44] F. Osareh, "Bibliometrics, citation analysis and co-citation analysis: a review of literature I," *Libri*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 149–158, 1996, doi: 10.1515/libr.1996.46.3.149.
- [45] VOSviewer, "VOSviewer - visualizing scientific landscapes," *VOSviewer*. Accessed: Aug. 16, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.vosviewer.com/>
- [46] H. Arruda, E. R. Silva, M. Lessa, D. Proença Jr., and R. Bartholo, "VOSviewer and bibliometrix," *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, vol. 110, no. 3, pp. 392–395, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.5195/jmla.2022.1434.
- [47] O. Debnath and H. N. Saha, "An IoT-based intelligent farming using CNN for early disease detection in rice paddy," *Microprocessors and Microsystems*, vol. 94, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.micpro.2022.104631.
- [48] M. Maray *et al.*, "Artificial intelligence-enabled coconut tree disease detection and classification model for smart agriculture," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 104, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2022.108399.
- [49] Z. Qiang and F. Shi, "Pest disease detection of brassica chinensis in wide scenes via machine vision: method and deployment," *Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection*, vol. 129, no. 3, pp. 533–544, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s41348-021-00562-8.
- [50] K. Ramana, R. Aluvala, M. R. Kumar, G. Nagaraja, A. V. Krishna, and P. Nagendra, "Leaf disease classification in smart agriculture using deep neural network architecture and IoT," *Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers*, vol. 31, no. 15, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1142/S0218126622400047.
- [51] E.-S. M. El-Kenawy *et al.*, "Metaheuristic optimization for improving weed detection in wheat images captured by drones," *Mathematics*, vol. 10, no. 23, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.3390/math10234421.
- [52] B. Yang *et al.*, "Identifying plant disease and severity from leaves: a deep multitask learning framework using triple-branch swin transformer and deep supervision," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 209, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2023.107809.
- [53] A. Albanese, M. Nardello, and D. Brunelli, "Automated pest detection with DNN on the edge for precision agriculture," *IEEE Journal on Emerging and Selected Topics in Circuits and Systems*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 458–467, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1109/JETCAS.2021.3101740.
- [54] S. Yang, "Identification of crop pests and diseases using a single convolutional neural network," in *2022 IEEE Conference on Telecommunications, Optics and Computer Science (TOCS)*, Dec. 2022, pp. 187–190, doi: 10.1109/TOCS56154.2022.10015910.
- [55] M. Khoshboresh-Masouleh and R. Shah-Hosseini, "Uncertainty estimation in deep meta-learning for crop and weed detection from multispectral UAV images," in *2022 IEEE Mediterranean and Middle-East Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium (M2GARSS)*, Mar. 2022, pp. 165–168, doi: 10.1109/M2GARSS52314.2022.9839758.
- [56] I. Sa *et al.*, "WeedNet: dense semantic weed classification using multispectral images and MAV for smart farming," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 588–595, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1109/LRA.2017.2774979.
- [57] J. Mathew, A. Joy, D. Sasi, J. Jiji, and J. John, "Crop prediction and plant disease detection using IoT and machine learning," in *2022 6th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI)*, Apr. 2022, pp. 560–565, doi: 10.1109/ICOEI53556.2022.9776852.

- [58] A. A. Bracino, R. S. Concepcion, R. A. R. Bedruz, E. P. Dadios, and R. R. P. Vicerra, "Development of a hybrid machine learning model for apple (*malus domestica*) health detection and disease classification," in *2020 IEEE 12th International Conference on Humanoid, Nanotechnology, Information Technology, Communication and Control, Environment, and Management (HNICEM)*, Dec. 2020, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/HNICEM51456.2020.9400139.
- [59] G. Garg, S. Gupta, P. Mishra, A. Vidyarthi, A. Singh, and A. Ali, "CROPCARE: an intelligent real-time sustainable iot system for crop disease detection using mobile vision," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 2840–2851, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2021.3109019.
- [60] R. G. de Luna, E. P. Dadios, and A. A. Bandala, "Automated image capturing system for deep learning-based tomato plant leaf disease detection and recognition," in *TENCON 2018 - 2018 IEEE Region 10 Conference*, Oct. 2018, pp. 1414–1419, doi: 10.1109/TENCON.2018.8650088.
- [61] T. Kalpana *et al.*, "An image based classification and prediction of diseases on cotton leaves using deep learning techniques," in *2023 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI56745.2023.10128306.
- [62] R. Lohith, K. E. Cholahgudda, and R. C. Biradar, "PyTorch implementation and assessment of pre-trained convolutional neural networks for tomato leaf disease classification," in *2022 IEEE Region 10 Symposium (TENSYP)*, Jul. 2022, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/TENSYP54529.2022.9864390.
- [63] P. Deepika and B. Arthi, "Prediction of plant pest detection using improved mask FRCNN in cloud environment," *Measurement: Sensors*, vol. 24, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2022.100549.
- [64] M. E. Karar, A.-H. Abdel-Aty, F. Algarni, M. F. Hassan, M. A. Abdou, and O. Reyad, "Smart IoT-based system for detecting RPW larvae in date palms using mixed depthwise convolutional networks," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 61, no. 7, pp. 5309–5319, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2021.10.050.
- [65] X. Fu *et al.*, "Crop pest image recognition based on the improved ViT method," *Information Processing in Agriculture*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 249–259, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.inpa.2023.02.007.
- [66] A. B. Kathole, K. Katti, S. Lonare, and G. Dharmale, "Identify and classify pests in the agricultural sector using metaheuristics deep learning approach," *Franklin Open*, vol. 3, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.fraope.2023.100024.
- [67] S. Kumi, D. Kelly, J. Woodstuff, R. K. Lomotey, R. Orji, and R. Deters, "Cocoa companion: deep learning-based smartphone application for cocoa disease detection," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 203, pp. 87–94, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2022.07.013.
- [68] H. H. Alshammari, A. I. Taloba, and O. R. Shahin, "Identification of olive leaf disease through optimized deep learning approach," *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, vol. 72, pp. 213–224, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.aej.2023.03.081.
- [69] N. Razfar, J. True, R. Bassiouny, V. Venkatesh, and R. Kashef, "Weed detection in soybean crops using custom lightweight deep learning models," *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research*, vol. 8, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.jafr.2022.100308.
- [70] K. L. Roldán-Serrato, J. A. S. Escalante-Estrada, and M. T. Rodríguez-González, "Automatic pest detection on bean and potato crops by applying neural classifiers," *Engineering in Agriculture, Environment and Food*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 245–255, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.eaef.2018.08.003.
- [71] K. K. Singh, "An artificial intelligence and cloud based collaborative platform for plant disease identification, tracking and forecasting for farmers," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing in Emerging Markets (CCEM)*, Nov. 2018, pp. 49–56, doi: 10.1109/CCEM.2018.00016.
- [72] C. Ashwini and V. Sellam, "Corn disease detection based on deep neural network for substantiating the crop yield," *Applied Mathematics & Information Sciences*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 423–433, May 2022, doi: 10.18576/amis/160304.
- [73] W.-L. Chen, Y.-B. Lin, F.-L. Ng, C.-Y. Liu, and Y.-W. Lin, "RiceTalk: rice blast detection using internet of things and artificial intelligence technologies," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 1001–1010, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1109/JIOT.2019.2947624.
- [74] N. G. Rezk, E. E.-D. Hemdan, A.-F. Attia, A. El-Sayed, and M. A. El-Rashidy, "An efficient IoT based framework for detecting rice disease in smart farming system," *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, vol. 82, no. 29, pp. 45259–45292, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11042-023-15470-2.
- [75] J. Wang, Y. Wu, Y. Zhang, H. Wang, H. Yan, and H. Jin, "A genetic algorithm-optimized backpropagation neural network model for predicting soil moisture content using spectral data," *Journal of Soils and Sediments*, vol. 24, no. 7, pp. 2816–2828, 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11368-024-03792-z.
- [76] U. N. Dulhare and S. Gouse, "Automation of rice cultivation from ploughing–harvesting with diseases, pests and weeds to increase the yield using AI," in *ICCCE 2021: Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Communications and Cyber Physical Engineering*, 2022, pp. 505–513, doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-7985-8_51.
- [77] S. Verma, A. Chug, and A. P. Singh, "Exploring capsule networks for disease classification in plants," *Journal of Statistics and Management Systems*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 307–315, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1080/09720510.2020.1724628.
- [78] K. Kumar, M. Padhiary, A. Hoque, P. Saikia, and C. Badgujar, "Self-service innovations in precision agriculture," in *Navigating the Self-Service Revolution with Smart Machines*, IGI Global, 2025, pp. 391–432, doi: 10.4018/979-8-3373-1295-8.ch014.
- [79] S. Yonbawi *et al.*, "Modeling of sensor enabled irrigation management for intelligent agriculture using hybrid deep belief network," *Computer Systems Science and Engineering*, vol. 46, no. 2, pp. 2319–2335, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.32604/csse.2023.036721.
- [80] A. Dahane, R. Benameur, and B. Kechar, "An IoT low-cost smart farming for enhancing irrigation efficiency of smallholders farmers," *Wireless Personal Communications*, vol. 127, no. 4, pp. 3173–3210, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s11277-022-09915-4.
- [81] P. M. Jacob, S. Suresh, J. M. John, P. Nath, P. Nandakumar, and S. Simon, "An intelligent agricultural field monitoring and management system using internet of things and machine learning," in *2020 International Conference on Data Analytics for Business and Industry: Way Towards a Sustainable Economy (ICDABI)*, Oct. 2020, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ICDABI51230.2020.9325612.
- [82] N. Kitpo, Y. Kugai, M. Inoue, T. Yokemura, and S. Satomura, "Internet of things for greenhouse monitoring system using deep learning and bot notification services," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics (ICCE)*, Jan. 2019, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICCE.2019.8661999.
- [83] N. Abdullah *et al.*, "Towards smart agriculture monitoring using fuzzy systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 4097–4111, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3041597.
- [84] F. E. Saheed, F. R. Pebriansyah, P. Sitorus, T. George Michael, and A. Turnip, "Development and implementation of smart irrigation for precision farming," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 1083, no. 1, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1083/1/012066.
- [85] A. Sumarudin, E. Ismantohadi, A. Puspaningrum, S. Maulana, and M. Nadi, "Implementation irrigation system using support vector machine for precision agriculture based on IoT," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1098, no. 3, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/1098/3/032098.

- [86] T. G. Michael, M. Turnip, E. Muniarti, E. Sitompul, and A. Turnip, "Development of an irrigation system for predicting watering time with anfis method for chili plants," *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, vol. 1083, no. 1, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1083/1/012081.
- [87] H. C. Pacco, "Simulation of temperature control and irrigation time in the production of tulips using Fuzzy logic," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 200, pp. 1–12, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2022.01.199.
- [88] B. Panigrahi, K. C. R. Kathala, and M. Sujatha, "A machine learning-based comparative approach to predict the crop yield using supervised learning with regression models," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 218, pp. 2684–2693, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2023.01.241.
- [89] S. Hemming, F. de Zwart, A. Elings, I. Righini, and A. Petropoulou, "Remote control of greenhouse vegetable production with artificial intelligence-greenhouse climate, irrigation, and crop production," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 8, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.3390/s19081807.
- [90] D. R. Vincent, N. Deepa, D. Elavarasan, K. Srinivasan, S. H. Chauhdary, and C. Iwendi, "Sensors driven AI-based agriculture recommendation model for assessing land suitability," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 17, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.3390/s19173667.
- [91] R. Mizuno, M. Goto, and H. Mineno, "Prediction method of plant irrigation timing considering data imbalance," *SMARTGREENS 2020 - Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Smart Cities and Green ICT Systems*, pp. 177–184, 2020, doi: 10.5220/0009339801770184.
- [92] R. K. M. Karthik and R. Kamalraj, "Smart manure recommendation using artificial intelligence," in *2022 International Interdisciplinary Humanitarian Conference for Sustainability (IIHC)*, Nov. 2022, pp. 1122–1127, doi: 10.1109/IIHC55949.2022.10059621.
- [93] J. Choi and N. Koshizuka, "Optimal harvest date prediction by integrating past and future feature variables," in *2019 IEEE Asia-Pacific Conference on Computer Science and Data Engineering (CSDE)*, Dec. 2019, pp. 1–8. doi: 10.1109/CSDE48274.2019.9162374.
- [94] C. Murugamani et al., "Machine learning technique for precision agriculture applications in 5G-based internet of things," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, vol. 2022, pp. 1–11, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/6534238.
- [95] I. Moutsinas et al., "AgroNIT: innovating precision agriculture," in *2022 Global Information Infrastructure and Networking Symposium (GIIS)*, Sep. 2022, pp. 6–12, doi: 10.1109/GIIS56506.2022.9937000.
- [96] T. Kawai and H. Mineno, "Evaluation environment using edge computing for artificial intelligence-based irrigation system," in *2020 16th International Conference on Mobility, Sensing and Networking (MSN)*, Dec. 2020, pp. 214–219, doi: 10.1109/MSN50589.2020.00046.
- [97] A. Bhardwaj, M. Kumar, M. Alshehri, I. Keshta, A. Abugabah, and S. K. Sharma, "Smart water management framework for irrigation in agriculture," *Environmental Technology*, vol. 45, no. 12, pp. 2320–2334, May 2024, doi: 10.1080/09593330.2022.2039783.
- [98] G. Patrizi, A. Bartolini, L. Ciani, V. Gallo, P. Sommella, and M. Carratu, "A virtual soil moisture sensor for smart farming using deep learning," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 71, pp. 1–11, 2022, doi: 10.1109/TIM.2022.3196446.
- [99] V. Nehra, A. Anand, and N. Kumari, "Fertilizer and crop recommendation using iout and machine learning," in *2023 13th International Conference on Cloud Computing, Data Science & Engineering (Confluence)*, Jan. 2023, pp. 629–634, doi: 10.1109/Confluence56041.2023.10048865.
- [100] B. Mahalakshmi, V. Sakthivel, B. S. Devi, and S. Swetha, "Agricultural crop and fertilizer recommendations based on various parameters," in *2023 International Conference on Sustainable Computing and Smart Systems (ICSCSS)*, Jun. 2023, pp. 735–739, doi: 10.1109/ICSCSS57650.2023.10169320.
- [101] L. Kanuru, A. K. Tyagi, A. S. U, T. F. Fernandez, N. Sreenath, and S. Mishra, "Prediction of pesticides and fertilizers using machine learning and internet of things," in *2021 International Conference on Computer Communication and Informatics (ICCCI)*, Jan. 2021, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICCCI50826.2021.9402536.
- [102] T. Thorat, B. K. Patle, and S. K. Kashyap, "Intelligent insecticide and fertilizer recommendation system based on TPF-CNN for smart farming," *Smart Agricultural Technology*, vol. 3, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.atech.2022.100114.
- [103] P. Radoglou-Grammatikis, P. Sarigiannidis, T. Lagkas, and I. Moscholios, "A compilation of UAV applications for precision agriculture," *Computer Networks*, vol. 172, May 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.comnet.2020.107148.
- [104] B. Swaminathan, S. Palani, S. Vairavasundaram, K. Kotecha, and V. Kumar, "IoT-driven artificial intelligence technique for fertilizer recommendation model," *IEEE Consumer Electronics Magazine*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 109–117, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1109/MCE.2022.3151325.
- [105] R. Donde et al., "Artificial intelligence and machine learning in rice research," in *Applications of Bioinformatics in Rice Research*, Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2021, pp. 239–275, doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-3997-5_12.
- [106] T. A. Shaikh, T. Rasool, and F. R. Lone, "Towards leveraging the role of machine learning and artificial intelligence in precision agriculture and smart farming," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 198, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2022.107119.
- [107] T. Saba, A. Rehman, K. Haseeb, S. A. Bahaj, and J. Lloret, "Trust-based decentralized blockchain system with machine learning using Internet of agriculture things," *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, vol. 108, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2023.108674.
- [108] A. Kumar, A. Rajanand, A. D. Kujur, Y. Rathore, and R. R. Janghel, "Segmentation of rice seedling using deep learning algorithm," in *2022 IEEE 11th International Conference on Communication Systems and Network Technologies (CSNT)*, Apr. 2022, pp. 164–168, doi: 10.1109/CSNT54456.2022.9787601.
- [109] A. H. Al-Badri, N. A. Ismail, K. Al-Dulaimi, A. Rehman, I. Abunadi, and S. A. Bahaj, "Hybrid CNN model for classification of rumex obtusifolius in Grassland," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 90940–90957, 2022, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3200603.
- [110] J.-F. Yeh, K.-M. Lin, C.-Y. Lin, and J.-C. Kang, "Intelligent mango fruit grade classification using alexnet-SPP with mask R-CNN-based segmentation algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on AgriFood Electronics*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 41–49, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1109/TAFE.2023.3267617.
- [111] Gunawan, M. Zarlis, P. Sihombing, and Sutorman, "Optimization of the CNN model for smart agriculture," *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 1088, no. 1, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1088/1757-899X/1088/1/012029.
- [112] H. M. Sahin, T. Miftahshudur, B. Grieve, and H. Yin, "Segmentation of weeds and crops using multispectral imaging and CRF-enhanced U-Net," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 211, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2023.107956.
- [113] S. C. V and T. R. Manjula, "An extensive study on satellite images of sentinel 2 for crop type identification," in *2023 International Conference on Advances in Electronics, Communication, Computing and Intelligent Information Systems (ICAECIS)*, Apr. 2023, pp. 668–675, doi: 10.1109/ICAECIS58353.2023.10170503.
- [114] K. Dilmurat, V. Sagan, and S. Moose, "AI-driven maize yield forecasting using unmanned aerial vehicle-based hyperspectral and lidar data fusion," *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. V-3–2022, pp. 193–199, May 2022, doi: 10.5194/isprs-annals-V-3-2022-193-2022.

- [115] L.-B. Chen, G.-Z. Huang, X.-R. Huang, and W.-C. Wang, "A self-supervised learning-based intelligent greenhouse orchid growth inspection system for precision agriculture," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 24, pp. 24567–24577, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2022.3221960.
- [116] D. Shadrin, A. Menshchikov, D. Ermilov, and A. Somov, "Designing future precision agriculture: detection of seeds germination using artificial intelligence on a low-power embedded system," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 19, no. 23, pp. 11573–11582, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2019.2935812.
- [117] S. Vashisht, P. Kumar, and M. C. Trivedi, "Crop yield prediction using improved extreme learning machine," *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 1–21, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1080/00103624.2022.2108828.
- [118] J. Morales-García, A. Bueno-Crespo, R. Martínez-España, and J. M. Cecilia, "Data-driven evaluation of machine learning models for climate control in operational smart greenhouses," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Smart Environments*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 3–17, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.3233/AIS-220441.
- [119] P. R. Karthikeyan *et al.*, "IoT based moisture control and temperature monitoring in smart farming," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1964, no. 6, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1964/6/062056.
- [120] P. D. Rosero-Montalvo, C. A. Gordillo-Gordillo, and W. Hernandez, "Smart farming robot for detecting environmental conditions in a greenhouse," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 57843–57853, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3283986.
- [121] S. B. Kamatchi and R. Parvathi, "Improvement of crop production using recommender system by weather forecasts," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 165, pp. 724–732, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2020.01.023.
- [122] C. Rawat, "AI for effective use of water in india for crop cultivation," *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 3s, pp. 266–270, 2023.
- [123] A. Hadidi, D. Saba, and Y. Sahli, "The role of artificial neuron networks in intelligent agriculture (case study: greenhouse)," 2021, pp. 45–67, doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-51920-9_4.
- [124] I. Beloev, D. Kinaneva, G. Georgiev, G. Hristov, and P. Zahariev, "Artificial intelligence-driven autonomous robot for precision agriculture," *Acta Technologica Agriculturae*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 48–54, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.2478/ata-2021-0008.
- [125] A. Roshanianfard, N. Noguchi, S. Ardabili, C. Mako, and A. Mosavi, "Autonomous robotic system for pumpkin harvesting," *Agronomy*, vol. 12, no. 7, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3390/agronomy12071594.
- [126] A. Yeshmukhametov, K. Koganezawa, Y. Yamamoto, Z. Buribayev, Z. Mukhtar, and Y. Amirgaliyev, "Development of continuum robot arm and gripper for harvesting cherry tomatoes," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 14, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3390/app12146922.
- [127] A. Sagheer, M. Mohammed, K. Riad, and M. Alhajhoj, "A cloud-based IoT platform for precision control of soilless greenhouse cultivation," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 1, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.3390/s21010223.
- [128] J. Han, L. Liu, and H. Zeng, "Design and implementation of intelligent agricultural picking mobile robot based on color sensor," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1757, no. 1, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1757/1/012157.
- [129] Y. He, F. Pan, B. Wang, Z. Teng, and J. Wu, "Transfer learning based fruits image segmentation for fruit-picking robots," in *2020 IEEE 3rd International Conference on Computer and Communication Engineering Technology (CCET)*, Aug. 2020, pp. 71–75, doi: 10.1109/CCET50901.2020.9213127.
- [130] G. S. P. Lakshmi, P. N. Asha, G. Sandhya, S. V. Sharma, S. Shilpashree, and S. G. Subramanya, "An intelligent IoT sensor coupled precision irrigation model for agriculture," *Measurement: Sensors*, vol. 25, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2022.100608.
- [131] M. S. Mahmud, A. Zahid, and A. K. Das, "Sensing and automation technologies for ornamental nursery crop production: current status and future prospects," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 4, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.3390/s23041818.
- [132] K. Endo, T. Kimura, N. Itoh, and T. Hiraguri, "Semantic segmentation based field detection using drones," in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics - Taiwan*, Jul. 2022, pp. 213–214, doi: 10.1109/ICCE-Taiwan55306.2022.9869088.
- [133] Y. Adhitya, S. W. Prakosa, M. Köppen, and J.-S. Leu, "Feature extraction for cocoa bean digital image classification prediction for smart farming application," *Agronomy*, vol. 10, no. 11, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.3390/agronomy10111642.
- [134] K.-Y. Li *et al.*, "Toward automated machine learning-based hyperspectral image analysis in crop yield and biomass estimation," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, no. 5, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.3390/rs14051114.
- [135] Z. Doshi, S. Nadkarni, R. Agrawal, and N. Shah, "Agroconsultant: intelligent crop recommendation system using machine learning algorithms," in *2018 Fourth International Conference on Computing Communication Control and Automation (ICCCUBEA)*, Aug. 2018, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/ICCCUBEA.2018.8697349.
- [136] S. D. Shingade, R. P. Mudhalwadkar, and K. M. Masal, "Random forest machine learning classifier for seed recommendation," in *2022 International Conference on Edge Computing and Applications (ICECAA)*, Oct. 2022, pp. 1385–1390, doi: 10.1109/ICECAA55415.2022.9936120.
- [137] O. Kudin, A. Kryvokhata, and V. I. Gorbenko, "Developing a deep learning sound classification system for a smart farming," *ECS Meeting Abstracts*, vol. MA2020-01, no. 26, pp. 1853–1853, 2020, doi: 10.1149/ma2020-01261853mtgabs.
- [138] S. M. Upadhyaya and S. Mathew, "Implementation of fuzzy logic in estimating yield of a vegetable crop," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1427, no. 1, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1427/1/012013.
- [139] V. Mamatha and J. C. Kavitha, "Machine learning based crop growth management in greenhouse environment using hydroponics farming techniques," *Measurement: Sensors*, vol. 25, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.measen.2023.100665.
- [140] N. S. Ouf, "Leguminous seeds detection based on convolutional neural networks: comparison of faster R-CNN and YOLOv4 on a small custom dataset," *Artificial Intelligence in Agriculture*, vol. 8, pp. 30–45, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.aiaa.2023.03.002.
- [141] J. P. Albarico, G. R. F. La Rosa, R. A. D. Santos, A. J. M. Tesorero, M. S. A. Magboo, and V. P. C. Magboo, "Roses greenhouse cultivation classification using machine learning techniques," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 218, pp. 2163–2171, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2023.01.192.
- [142] C.-J. Lee, M.-D. Yang, H.-H. Tseng, Y.-C. Hsu, Y. Sung, and W.-L. Chen, "Single-plant broccoli growth monitoring using deep learning with UAV imagery," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 207, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.compag.2023.107739.
- [143] A. G. Pereira, L. Porwol, A. Ojo, and E. Curry, "Towards a temporal deep learning model to support sustainable agricultural practices," *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, vol. 2563, pp. 152–163, 2019.
- [144] R. Singh, S. Srivastava, and R. Mishra, "AI and IoT based monitoring system for increasing the yield in crop production," in *2020 International Conference on Electrical and Electronics Engineering (ICE3)*, Feb. 2020, pp. 301–305, doi: 10.1109/ICE348803.2020.9122894.
- [145] S. Rajput, L. Khanna, and P. Kumari, "Artificial intelligence and machine learning-based agriculture," *Smart Village Infrastructure and Sustainable Rural Communities*, IGI Global, 2023, pp. 16–34, doi: 10.4018/978-1-6684-6418-2.ch002.
- [146] Y. Di, M. Gao, F. Feng, Q. Li, and H. Zhang, "A new framework for winter wheat yield prediction integrating deep learning and bayesian optimization," *Agronomy*, vol. 12, no. 12, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.3390/agronomy12123194.

- [147] M. da C. Borba, J. E. S. Ramos, B. M. Ramborger, E. O. Marques, and J. A. D. Machado, "Agricultural management through artificial intelligence: an analysis of digitization of agriculture (in Portuguese: *Gestão no meio agrícola com o apoio da Inteligência Artificial: uma análise da digitalização da agricultura*)," *Revista em Agronegócio e Meio Ambiente*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1–22, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.17765/2176-9168.2022v15n3e9337.
- [148] D.-H. Lee, H.-J. Kim, and J.-H. Park, "UAV, a farm map, and machine learning technology convergence classification method of a corn cultivation area," *Agronomy*, vol. 11, no. 8, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.3390/agronomy11081554.
- [149] L.-W. Liu, C.-T. Lu, Y.-M. Wang, K.-H. Lin, X. Ma, and W.-S. Lin, "Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) growth modeling based on growth degree day (GDD) and artificial intelligence algorithms," *Agriculture*, vol. 12, no. 1, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.3390/agriculture12010059.
- [150] O. Iparraguirre-Villanueva *et al.*, "Disease identification in crop plants based on convolutional neural networks," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 14, no. 3, 2023, doi: 10.14569/IJACSA.2023.0140360.
- [151] M. D. B. Yousefi *et al.*, "Classification of oil palm female inflorescences anthesis stages using machine learning approaches," *Information Processing in Agriculture*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 537–549, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.inpa.2020.11.007.
- [152] H. Rosnan and N. Yusof, "Digital technologies and small-scale rural farmers in Malaysia," *Digitalisation: Opportunities and Challenges for Business*, 2023, pp. 776–783, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-26953-0_72.
- [153] S. Chakraborty, N. Choudhury, and I. Kalita, "AI-based smart agriculture monitoring using ground-based and remotely sensed images," in *The New Advanced Society*, Wiley, 2022, pp. 191–221, doi: 10.1002/9781119884392.ch9.
- [154] R. Thangamani, D. Sathya, G. K. Kamalam, and G. N. Lyer, "AI green revolution: reshaping agriculture's future," *Intelligent Robots and Drones for Precision Agriculture*, 2024, pp. 421–461, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-51195-0_19.

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